

‘Amra kara? Bastuhara. We are the dispossessed’¹ : climate refugees in Amitav Ghosh’s *The Hungry Tide* and *Gun Island*

Sejal Mahendru

“...no one leaves home until home
is a damp voice in your ear saying
leave, run now, I don't know what I've become”
[“Conversations on Home (at a deportation center)”,
Warsan Shire]

These lines, by the British-Somali poet Warsan Shire, were written after the death of a young Syrian boy, Aylan Kurdi, whose body washed ashore the Mediterranean coast after his family was denied refuge and stranded at sea. Shire’s poem not only invokes the sufferings of the refugee and reaffirms their humanity (a figure whose representation has historically been dominated with images of indistinguishable masses to create a rhetoric of fear), but also portends a different kind of loss: that of the immutability and disappearance of home itself. This

dispossession emerging out of the disappearance of ecological spaces has become an imminent eventuality at a time when rising sea-levels, increasing droughts, unpredictable and harsher weather-events, as well as toxicity and pollution, are making certain places around the world increasingly uninhabitable. This is especially true for vulnerable communities that rely on the land for subsistence and do not have resources to withstand extreme environmental calamities. Andrew Baldwin has coined the term “Anthropocene mobilities” to emphasize the phenomenon that the environment is “the very material substance through which mobility itself is mediated, experienced, and conceptualized” (Baldwin, 290). This inequality across axes of class, race and national identity leads to restriction and vilification of bodies in motion within and especially between nations, as evidenced through the growing rhetoric against immigration, especially from the Global South to North. The growing wave of racially-charged policies targeting Latino communities in the US, South-Asians in the UK and Canada, and Bangladeshis in India, all point to a collective geopolitical crisis.

As we grapple with this rise in anti-immigrant rhetoric around the world, it is a crucial time to contend with how literature, as a mode of cultural resistance, can provide a discursive counter to this fear-mongering and reinstate the humanity of the migrant. One such writer, who acknowledges the challenges in writing fiction that

appropriately addresses contemporary environmental issues and its effects on public perception, is Amitav Ghosh. Ghosh is one of few contemporary writers who have consciously incorporated environmental issues into most of their writings. His book *The Great Derangement* (2016) is a self-reflexive study of the shortcomings of contemporary fiction, especially the novel, in adequately communicating the climate crisis in the face of rampant misinformation and denial. While Ghosh's literary works deal with climate change in its multivalence, for the purposes of this paper, I examine his handling of climate migration in the novels *The Hungry Tide* (2004) and *Gun Island* (2019) to explore how this elusive categorization plays out in fiction. Through a reading of the two novels in conjunction with the political realities they represent—both novels deal with refugee crises that have occurred in history: across India-Bangladesh in the 1970s, and from the Middle East to Europe in the 2010s— I wish to explore literature's discursive potential in countering the growing anti-immigration rhetoric of the 21st century.

The staggering scale of climate migration has been widely prophesied in recent years. The International Panel on Climate Change estimates that a total of 200 million people will be displaced due to environmental causes by the year 2050 (Brown, 12), yet the figure of the climate refugee is fraught with misconceptions that pose a unique representational challenge. There is lack of a legal framework that protects the rights of climate

migrants: the United Nations High Commission for Refugees, often considered the rubric for international cases report on refugees does not identify environmental migration², an oversight that was tested in January 2020 when Ioane Teitota, an asylum seeker from Kiribati facing deportation in New Zealand, appealed to the United Nations that the imminent submersion of his island country should be grounds for protecting his status as a climate refugee. Teitota's case and UN's favorable resolution have set a global precedent and brought attention to the reality of climate immigration. However, the absence of any international agreement leaves the future of climate refugees uncertain.

In addition to the lack of legal protection, the undefined contours of climate migration pose a challenge to the literary and artistic works that seek to center anthropogenic climate change and its effects. In his book *Slow Violence and the Environmentalism of the Poor*, Rob Nixon defines environmental violence as “occurring gradually and out of sight, a violence of delayed destruction that is dispersed across time and space, an attritional violence that is typically not viewed as violence at all” (Nixon, 4). Since the conditions that drive climate migration are less tangible than other forms of violence and consequently do not register as violence in public memory, the phenomenon poses a representational challenge in our current technological age where audiences are used to spectacle and immediacy to be spurred into action. The

historian Dipesh Chakraborty further stretches Nixon's idea of slow violence to consider its geological scales. In the essay "The Climate of History: Four Theses", Chakraborty highlights how "anthropogenic explanations of climate change spell the collapse of the age-old humanist distinction between natural history and human history" (Chakraborty, 2011) by causing atmospheric and geological changes- such as a sustained increase in global carbon emissions- that will unfold over millennia. Thus, human history, measured on a scale of several thousand years, is now inextricable from geological history which has been measured on a much larger timeline. This conflation not only results in a paradigmatic shift in the way history and time are conceptualized, but it also signals a blind spot in literary renditions of climatological issues, where writers struggle with this problem of merging past, present and future. "Crises of climate change produce anxieties precisely around pasts that we cannot comprehend and futures that we cannot visualize", Chakraborty claims. This sentiment that is echoed in *The Great Derangement*, where Ghosh calls literature's inability to address issues of scale a "cultural and imaginative failure" (*The Great Derangement*, 23). The climate crisis is the uncanny, writes Ghosh, and works of fiction that attempt to represent the vast scope of the Anthropocene are often unceremoniously eschewed from the high-echelons of literary realism into the literary realm of the fantastical, an outdated mode of literary criticism that nevertheless helps the readers dissociate from their own

surroundings. Ghosh's argument that literature needs to embrace the uncanny is echoed by Urusla Kluwick, who considers instances of environmental migration and border-crossing as "moments of eruption" where the effects of climate change become visible and legible in an otherwise nebulous system (Kluwick, 509), making it particularly appealing for contemporary environmental writers.

In this regard, both *The Hungry Tide* and *Gun Island* counter this restrictive view of realism by anchoring their plots around real immigration crises and embedding the climatic uncanny within them. Set in the Sundarbans, the plot of *The Hungry Tide* explores the environmental anxieties that lie at the heart of India's treatment of vulnerable migrants, by juxtaposing two timelines. The novel's narrative is split between the early years of the twenty-first century and the 1970s. The novel's contemporary timeline is narrated through the split points-of-view of Kanai Dutt and Piya Roy, two visitors to the Sundarbans. Kanai is a middle-aged, Delhi-based translator visiting his aunt in Lusibari (a small town on the edges of the Sundarbans mangrove) after the death of his uncle Nirmal, while Piya is an American cetologist born to Bengali immigrants, who has come to the delta to observe the Irrawaddy dolphin. Their paths cross on the train to the Sundarbans where Kanai invites her to his aunt's house with the intention of romantically pursuing her. Over the course of the novel, Kanai acts as a translator for

Piya as she ventures into the riverine islands with Fokir, a fisherman and the son of Kusum, Kanai's childhood friend who was killed in the Marichjhapi massacre.

The novel connects the timelines of the past and present through an epistolary narrative that begins with the posthumous discovery of a journal belonging to Kanai's uncle Nirmal, which details his witnessing of the Indian state's assassination of Bangladeshi refugees during the Marichjhapi massacre of 1979. Nirmal's journal offers the narrative an opportunity at historical recovery and informs Kanai (and by extension, the reader) about the complicity of the Indian state when (after cyclone Bhola rendered parts of the Bangladeshi coast uninhabitable) hundreds of climate refugees crossed the porous mangrove borders into India. Ghosh exposes several layers of environmental injustice and dispossession enacted upon this community. The upper-caste settlers were allotted coastal settlements in West Bengal, enabling not only economic but also environmental rehabilitation. However, this poor community of fisherman and farmers who belonged to a Dalit tribal communities, were forcibly relocated to a refugee settlement in the Dandakaranya region of Madhya Pradesh in central India.

In their book *Ecology and Equity: The Use and Abuse of Nature in Contemporary India*, Ramachandra Guha and Madhav Gadgil categorize three tiers of ecological communities in India: the Omnivores that have manipulated

nature such as those who live in urban centers which includes the lawmakers; the ecosystem people who subsist off their land and immediate environment such as indigenous tribes and to an extent rural farmers; and ecological refugees who emerge when ecosystem people are dispossessed from their environments due to the actions of the omnivores, such as those displaced due to deforestation or development projects. Guha and Gadgil's analysis can be fittingly applied to the displaced community in *The Hungry Tide*. The refugees refuse to remain in these internment camps and march to Marichjhapi, an uninhabited island in the Sundarbans that the state government had reserved for tiger conservation. The refugees' eventual unlawful settlement in Marichjhapi had as much to do with the paltry conditions of the camps, as it had with the fact that the environmental conditions in the dry, arid region put them at a severe disadvantage as they could not successfully farm or hunt in these areas. This recognition of denial of the habitat that the refugees required to thrive in favor of tiger conservation efforts, reveals yet another way in which social hierarchies determine environmental justice, and complicates the question of environmental migration and refugee rehabilitation in our current global situation. The novel ties its narrative to the historical event of the Marichjhapi massacre through the character of Kusum, a poor girl from the Indian side of the Sundarbans who had to move to the mainland after her father was killed by the tigers. When Kusum hears about the refugee set-

tlers' march she decides to join them to return to her native land. This cross-border solidarity between Kusum and the Bangladeshi refugees further strengthens the arbitrary nature of national borders, as Kusum realizes she has much more in common with them than with the Indian citizens of the mainland: "These were my people", muses Kusum, "We shared the same tongue... the dreams they had were not different from my own. They too had hankered for our tide country mud, they too had longed to watch the tide rise to full flood." (*The Hungry Tide*, 165) Kusum's words invoke the absurdity of the national border between India and Bangladesh, which was created in 1947 after the partition of India and East Pakistan, and turned neighbors and community members into foreigners and adversaries overnight. This dissonance between ecological belonging and national identity is further questioned when Kusum's return to Marichjhapi turns her from a native to a refugee and eventually to an intruder when she, along with the other settlers, refuse to leave the island. Kusum's Indian citizenship and her roots in the Sundarbans are not enough to protect her when the state government blocks off the supply of food and drinking water to the island, and eventually sends in law enforcement to forcibly evacuate the settlers, dead or alive.

The Hungry Tide further reveals how environmental disasters magnify and exacerbate the existing socio-political inequalities. The migrants of Marichjhapi were members

of the Hindu minority in Bangladesh who were doubly marginalized due to their religion and within that, their caste. This discrimination also prompted the move across the border to India when the cyclone submerged parts of the coast. While caste discrimination is legally prohibited in the Indian constitution, the Marichjhapi massacre- carried out by the contemporary state government in West Bengal- is a firm reminder that not only do forms of systemic discrimination result in economic inequalities with the denial of equal opportunities and the propagation of generational wealth, but that these markers of identity also influence one's ability to cross regions and borders.

The Hungry Tide tells the stories of many characters who cross national and international borders, and the legitimacy of these movements is determined by their socio-economic status and the labels those generate. From Kanai, the Delhi-based translator who goes to the Sundarbans on a whim, to Piya, the marine biologist from Oregon who travels to the Sundarbans as an international researcher to study the changing migratory patterns of the Gangetic Irrawady dolphins (another direct result of climate change and warming seas), there are many migrants in the world of the novel. In contrast to these cosmopolitan tourists, the "refugee" Kusum, and her son Fokir, are native to the Sundarbans, having grown up in the unique terrain of the mangrove forest, and intimately familiar with the flora and fauna that are found there. That they are the ones who are relegated to the

status of refugees and subjected to the violence that the term engenders may seem like a cruel twist of fate, but actually reveals both the arbitrariness of national borders, as well as the links between ecological and social injustice.

The Marichjhapi massacre is a strong reminder of the terrible fate that might await more climate refugees as the climate crisis deepens, unless there is a stronger mechanism to protect the humanity of the migrants. The novel is especially relevant in light of the ongoing tensions over the Citizenship Amendment Act in India. The Act, passed in 2019 (this time under the Right-wing central government led by the Bhartiya Janata Party), aims to provide asylum to refugees that belong to religious minorities from India's neighboring Muslim-majority Nations, excluding Muslim asylum seekers. Furthermore, the government has launched a National Register of Citizens, which has already been implemented in the Indian state of Assam that borders Bangladesh, and includes a caveat for collecting information on residents whose citizenship cannot be sufficiently proven. These laws are seen by many as an attempt to disenfranchise anyone who does not have sufficient documentation at a time when concerns about climate migration across this border are increasing.

While *The Hungry Tide* complicates the question of environmental rehabilitation of refugees by stressing on the injustice of environmental (and historical) erasure,

Gun Island looks beyond the specificities of localized environments towards what Lucinda Newns, in her essay “The Sea Cannot be Fenced: “Natural” and “Unnatural” Borders in Gloria Anzaldúa’s *Borderlands/La Frontera* and Amitav Ghosh’s *Gun Island*”, terms a trans-local ecology-

Rather than asserting any essential connection between people and their environment as a way of deconstructing bordering processes, *Gun Island* evokes a mobile or, more specifically, translocal form of ecology that emphasizes connections—human and non-human—between locations with otherwise differing cultures, languages, and positions in the capitalist world system. (Newns, 11)

The concept of translocality rejects the hierarchical relationship between natives and immigrants that bioregionalism prioritizes, and instead emphasizes the shared ecological experiences of communities around the world. Newns argues that while *The Hungry Tide* invokes the refugees’ ties to the land to critique the Indian state’s settler-colonialism, this essentializing impulse can also work to delegitimize the presence of “outsiders” in the face of global climate change and its resultant mobilities. *Gun Island* problematizes this discourse by considering the truly global scale of the climate crisis and investigates the position of the climate migrant beyond the bioregion to which one natively belongs by highlighting the connections between what seem to be separate, unconnected weather events. The novel contains a vast number of

characters who live in different parts of the world, and their encounters, as well as the relationships they develop, help create a story in which extreme weather events such as forest fires in the Pacific northwest, hailstorms in Italy in the summer, increasing frequency of cyclones in the Bay of Bengal and the beaching of dolphins, are brought into conversation as manifestations of a shared ecological crisis.

Ghosh's situation of both these novels within history also works to legitimize climate migration as a historical phenomenon that predates the modern nation-state and highlights the arbitrariness of national borders. While *The Hungry Tide* achieves this by uncovering the massacre of India's first climate refugees, *Gun Island* examines the relationship between past and present through a historical and geographical mapping of a mythological legend. The plot of *Gun Island* is interspersed with mentions of the travels and travails of the Banduki Saudagar (Gun Merchant), a mythical hero-pirate who tries to flee the wrath of the snake goddess Manasa Devi, and sails to Europe from South Asia to escape the storms and cyclones she sends his way. The Banduki Saudagar thus emerges as a historical climate refugee, whose tale animates the experiences of present-day migrants such as the novel's protagonist Deen Dutta, a historian and rare-book dealer from New York who, on an annual visit to his family in Kolkata, visits the Gun Merchant's shrine in the Sundarbans. History factors heavily into the way

the present operates in the novel. When Deen's friend Cinta, a celebrated Italian historian enters the narrative, the two begin to trace connections between the myth of the Banduki Saudagar and actual historical weather events, showing that what exists today as myth actually has roots in history. A brief account of an academic conference that Deen and Cinta attend includes a presentation on the historic climate migration ushered by the Little Ice Age of the seventeenth century. A chance mention of the Taj Mahal during this presentation triggers Deen into making connections between the events of the Little Ice Age and the places mentioned in the Banduki Saudagar's accounts-

That took my mind back to India, and it occurred to me that the temples of Bishnupur were built at about the same time. This in turn reminded me of the Gun Merchant's shrine . . . and I suddenly recalled the droughts, famines, storms and plagues that played so large a part in the legend. Was it possible that the legend was born of the tribulations of the Little Ice Age? (Gun Island, 136)

As the novel proceeds, Deen and Cinta continue to decipher geographical locations embedded in the myth to emphasize the timelessness of human environmental migration. They realize that the Merchant was called Banduki not because of the Hindi/Bangla word for gun "banduk", but because of the Arabic-Byzantine name for Venice, Banadiq. Taal misrir desh, a major stop in the

Gun Merchant's journey is revealed to be not sugar-candy land (from the Bangla word *misri* for sugar), but Egypt, from the Arabic word *Misr* (Gun Island, 151). The Gun Merchant's path thus illuminates the current migratory patterns of climate refugees in the novel, who move from the uncertain shores of Bangladesh to the Middle East and Africa to find refuge in Europe.

As the pieces of this puzzle come together, the narrative introduces us to several other wanderers, whose status as traveler/settler/refugee is dependent on their socio-political identities. The novel is written as a loose sequel to *The Hungry Tide*, with Piya (now dividing her time travelling between Oregon and the Sundarbans, living as a resident in both places) as the main recurring character. The mobility of characters like Deen, Cinta, and Piya, who travel from New York to New Delhi to the Sundarbans to Venice to California, is pitted against the refugee characters Tipu and Rafi, a young gay couple who escapes the Sundarbans hinterlands, both due to its environmental vulnerability, but also because the state seems to have accepted its imminent destruction and made it a place without a future. Their journey to find asylum takes them to Bangladesh, back to the Indian mainland, then Pakistan, Iran Turkey, Libya, and Egypt as they finally make their way on to the shores of Italy. This journey, beset with human traffickers, hostile law enforcement, and apathetic governments, is revealed to be eerily akin to that of the Gun Merchant. The novel

sets these journeys up to show the vast inequalities that govern global systems of mobility and culminates in a fictional recreation of the European refugee crisis of 2015, when, in the aftermath of the Syrian war, an estimated 1.3 million refugees arrived in Europe. Heads of state of several countries like Greece and Italy refused to allow boats to dock on their shores, leading to the deaths of hundreds of migrants. *Gun Island* thus extends the scope of climate migration to include not just immediate disasters, but the imminent ones that result from the slow violence of the Anthropocene, and highlights the similarities that can still be traced between historic and contemporary events.

Through Tipu and Rafi, Ghosh allows the readers to glimpse the human face of the climate refugee. According to Matthew Schneider-Meyerson and Giovanni Bettini, literary works that represent climate refugees as faceless masses inadvertently generate fear in the environmentally secure, and feeds into larger anti-immigrant sentiment³ that often mingles with racism. In this light, *Gun Island's* etching out of individual refugee personalities, as young men and women with dreams, humour, flaws, and love, offers an alternative that tackles the problem of scale without erasing the individuality of the migrants. It is in this novel that Ghosh makes a stronger case for the humanity of the dispossessed. While *The Hungry Tide* had clear sympathies with the refugees of Marichjhapi, the actual refugees- Kusum (and to a lesser extent her son Fokir)- were presented through the per-

spectives of the privileged, upper caste Kanai, Nirmal, and Piya, who initially viewed them as foils to their own characters, and then, even as their bonds developed, as objects of their respective desires. Beyond Kusum and Fokir, we actually never hear from the actual refugees that crossed the border, and the one time we do, it is through Nirmal's distanced perspective. Nirmal's journal reveals that as he arrived at Marichjhapi during the state's crackdown on the migrants, from the safe distance of the bhotbhoti (boat), he heard a chorus of defiance on the shore: "we heard the settlers shouting a refrain: 'Marichjhapi chharbona. We'll not leave Marichjhapi, do what you may.'" Standing on the deck of the bhotbhoti, I was struck by the beauty of this. Where else could you belong, except in the place you refused to leave. I joined my feeble voice to theirs: Marichjhapi chharbona!" (*The Hungry Tide*, 254) Nirmal's admiration for the collectivity and defiance notwithstanding, we do not get to see the migrants as individuals beyond their plight as refugees.

On the other hand, *Gun Island* not only legitimizes the concerns of the refugees, but also presents the readers with their voices and the multiplicity of their perspectives through Tipu, Rafi, and the other Bengali refugees in Venice. The narrative traces the journey and growth of Tipu, another character from *The Hungry Tide*- Fokir's son who earlier went by Tutul. In a way, the narrative works as a minor bildungsroman touching upon Tipu's experiences with his father's death, his attempts at fitting in in the USA as Piya's ward, his return to India, his

plans to escape the lack of opportunity and imminent collapse of the ways of life in the Sundarbans, and his coming to terms with his sexuality and desire to build a life with Rafi in Europe.

Through the representation of the refugee characters, *Gun Island* challenges the discourse about the primitivism of ecosystem people and counters concerns about their assimilation in a modern society. Both Tipu and Rafi, while economically impoverished, display a technological aptitude and intelligence that forces the middle-class Deen to confront his bourgeois biases about poverty and migrants. “Tourists are often surprised to see we have cellphones here”, says Rafi in response to Deen’s surprise. (*Gun Island*, 94) In this interaction, it is Deen who is revealed to be the unaware outsider, even though his status as a tourist offers him more mobility across national lines. Deen’s astonishment at Rafi’s adeptness with satellite phones, and his medicinal knowledge when Tipu is bitten by a King Cobra, work to challenge the readers’ own biases about climate refugees and their ability to assimilate, and also posits technology as a means of connecting different parts of the world. Rafi tells Deen that people living in remote areas like the Sundarbans not only have greater need of the internet and access to GPS and weather reports, but this technology also allows them to dream of a better life by introducing the existence of different places and possibilities. “The Internet is the migrants’ magic carpet” Tipu tells Deen, “It’s their conveyor belt. It doesn’t matter

whether they are travelling by plane or bus or boat; it's the Internet that moves the wetware." (*Gun Island*, 61). The novel's progress emphasizes this recognition of the connection between climate migrants and contemporary media and technology. Deen (and the readers) are made aware of Tipu's struggles as an asylum seeker through his email correspondence. The novel's climax, where a boat full of supporters goes to protect the incoming migrant ship against the attack from an anti-immigration militia, is able to garner public support through a social media campaign organized by Rafi.

Gun Island further dismantles the prevailing narrative about immigration as a drain on the host country by highlighting the contributions of the Bangladeshi migrant community in Venice. On a visit to Venice, Deen once again encounters Rafi, who had gotten separated from Tipu on their journey, and who now lives in the Venice ghetto and works under the table to pay the traffickers to get Tipu across. Lubna, a former immigrant who now runs an organization to help the newer arrivals, informs Deen that the Venice ghetto houses a community of migrants who work jobs such as construction and selling goods which are crucial to Venice's economic functioning while they live in extreme poverty and uncertainty-

most of them work all day long, doing several different jobs. They barely get any sleep. On top of that, some of them haven't yet had their incontro – that's

the meeting with the committee that decides on their status. And I'm sad to say there have been problems in the past for those who spoke with journalists – anything they say to the media can be used against them. You understand? And there are other problems as well. Sometimes right-wing troublemakers see things on television and get all worked up – you know how things are nowadays. (*Gun Island*, 176)

This illustration of the refugees' lives challenges xenophobic descriptions that paint them as being dependent on state welfare and drives home the precariousness of their existence.

Literature that seeks to empathetically portray climate migration has to consistently overcome the issue of geographical scale, and create tales that can resonate globally, without losing sight of the localized differences of environmental experiences. In her book *Sense of Place and Sense of Planet*, Ursula Heise highlights the dilemma that has punctuated theories of environmental justice across the world: “some theorists criticize nationally based forms of identity and hold out cosmopolitan identifications as a plausible and politically preferable alternative, other scholars emphasize the importance of holding on to national and local modes of belonging as a way of resisting the imperialism of some forms of globalization.” (Heise, 17) This dichotomy becomes especially relevant in the context of climate migration where, while theories of place are extremely important in order to under-

stand how environmental habits in one corner of the world can have drastic effects in another, the globe can function as an effective discursive trope to counter the rhetoric of nationalism and difference in favor of representing a shared humanity. This simultaneous exploration of vast geographical and temporal distances often teeters on the periphery of what is considered improbable, another criticism that Ghosh attempts to address in *The Great Derangement* as indicative of older forms of edification that no longer hold true in our current environmental moment. He mentions how his experience of a rare tornado in Delhi in the 1970s had been formative for his development as a writer, yet he always avoided including that incident in his writings for fear of being written off. But in *Gun Island*, Ghosh includes an incident where Venice sees a similarly uncharacteristic hailstorm, no longer as an anomaly but as an indicator of unpredictable weather patterns that are the result of global climate change. As the writer Rajat Chaudhary states in his review of *Gun Island*, “because climate change knows no boundaries and can spring surprises and violent retribution at a place of its choosing, and also because stories connect with stories riding microscopic filaments of probability and chance, the characters of *Gun Island* find out how an angry planet stitches them together in the present, as it had in the past, when the gun merchant was running away from a wrathful goddess.” (Chaudhary, 1) This deliberate undercutting of the supposed boundaries of realism allows for a merging of the global

and local through climate change, and helps readers far away from the locus of the action to understand the motivating factors that would drive people to seek shelter in distant lands. The climax of the novel, where a group of dolphins interrupt the stand-off between the refugee boat and the Italian navy and lead to a change of heart from the admiral, is another instance of the uncanny, a moment of eruption and spectacle that the novel form employs to speculate on a positive outcome for climate refugees.

Gun Islands's optimistic conclusion seems to find resonance in recent developments. On December 09 2022, Pradyut Bordoloi, a Member of Parliament from the state of Assam, and a member of the Indian National Congress (currently the leading opposition party in the country) introduced the Climate Migrants (Protection and Rehabilitation) Bill in the Lok Sabha. The bill proposes funding for both immediate as well as protracted weather events. In an interview with *Scroll Magazine*, Bordoloi highlights the limitations of the current climate law, the National Action for Climate Change passed in 2008 for being “geared more towards short-term and sudden-onset climatic disasters [and] ignoring slow climatic changes”. Bordoloi explains that “The Brahmaputra River system is dotted with islands where mostly people of migrant origin, usually from the minority community, settle down...Earlier, the life cycle of an established riverine island [till it would get submerged] would be

around 20 years. But, of late, in the last 10 years or so, because of the erratic water flow in the Brahmaputra, it's gone down to four-five years." The proposed bill thus attempts to redefine the scale of climate catastrophes to account for slow-acting factors. The bill also focuses on issues of rehabilitation, especially for communities that rely on specific environmental factors for their lifestyle and traditions, and recognizes the nexus between social and environmental exploitation within India's unique social context of class, caste, and religion. There are still several challenges, however. The bill needs to pass in the Indian Parliament which currently has a majority by the BJP and its allies. And despite Bordoloi's comments about the need to consider migrants from Bangladesh in the grand scheme of things, the bill solely focuses on migration within India. Nevertheless, the language of the draft reveals that cultural conversations around the topic of climate migration have evolved to consider the issue of slow violence and its resultant geopolitical complexities.

Thus, while there are several challenges in the path of creating an empathetic narrative that centers climate migrants, Ghosh's attempts in this series of books present a promising shift in the zeitgeist, and offer an example of how the novel form can tell stories that operate within spatio-temporal scales that can adequately address the scope of climate migration in the Anthropocene. *The Hungry Tide* and *Gun Island* ought to be read as strong

proponents of environmental justice that present climate migration as a global humanitarian crisis and challenge the prevailing discourse on refugees.

NOTES:

1. *The Hungry Tide*, 254

2. The definition of refugee status laid out in 1951 by the United Nations High Commission for Refugees, states that a refugee is any person who, “owing to well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership in a particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of his nationality and is unable or, owing to such fear, unwilling to avail himself of the protection of that country; or who, not having a nationality and being outside the country of his former habitual residence as a result of such events, is unable, or, owing to such fear, unwilling to return to it” (McKee, 315)

3. Matthew Schneider-Mayerson, “Just as in the Book? The Influence of Literature on Readers’ Awareness of Climate Injustice and Perception of Climate Migrants”. Giovanni Bettini, “Climate Barbarians at the Gate? A critique of apocalyptic narratives on climate refugees”

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